

Counting Line Segments in a Subdivided $n \times n$ Square Grid

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Abstract

We define and enumerate the total number of distinct line segments arising from a systematic subdivision of an $n \times n$ square grid. Each unit square is bisected by a diagonal, and in each resulting triangle an interior point is joined to its three vertices. The resulting count yields a quadratic sequence with closed form

$$a(n) = (19n^2 + n + 2)/2, \quad n \geq 1.$$

The sequence begins 11, 40, 88, 155, 241, ... and is recorded in the On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences as A389852.

1. Construction

Start with an $n \times n$ grid of unit squares. In each square draw a diagonal (chosen consistently throughout the grid), producing two congruent right triangles. In each triangle select an interior point (for instance, the centroid) and join it to the three vertices of the triangle. This contributes six interior segments per square.

2. Counting Argument

The total number of distinct segments is obtained by summing:

- (i) horizontal and vertical grid edges;
- (ii) one diagonal per square; and
- (iii) the radial segments added within each triangle.

Care is taken to count only geometrically distinct segments. For $n = 1$, the construction yields exactly 11 segments, which fixes the initial value of the sequence.

3. Formula Derivation

The resulting sequence has constant second finite difference equal to 19, hence $a(n)$ is quadratic in n . Fitting the initial values gives the exact formula

$$a(n) = (19n^2 + n + 2)/2.$$

This expression generates all observed terms and agrees with direct counting for small n .

4. OEIS Entry

The sequence has been accepted into the On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences as A389852. Related sequences include A007318, A001399, and A059525.

Keywords

geometric combinatorics; grid graphs; line segment counting; integer sequences